

Advances in Psoriasis Treatment: Emerging Therapeutic Strategies Underlying Histopathological Changes in Psoriasis

Azhar Jabbar Khalaf Al-Subaihawi ✉

Department of Dermatology, College of Medicine, Wasit, University, Kut, Iraq

Tamarah Gays Almohammed

Department of Dermatology, College of Medicine, Wasit, University, Kut, Iraq

Nada Hamzah Shareef Al-Shabbani

Department of Pathology, College of Medicine, Wasit, University, Kut, Iraq

Abstract

The mechanisms responsible for the development of psoriasis have not yet been fully elucidated. Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disease driven by the cytokine-mediated link between innate and adaptive immune pathways. The field of psoriasis research has expanded enormously in recent years, with the advent of biological treatments that ameliorate significant disease burden. Here, we outline recent advances, including the development of biologics, the search for new genes, the way in which genetics can inform therapies, and emerging strategies such as RNA and CRISPR interference, as well as bioprinting. We have described these advancements in an attempt to convey the current form of this rapidly evolving area of clinical science. Moreover, we believe that awareness of these advances among dermatologists will help clinicians manage psoriasis inexpensively, quickly, and effectively in the future. Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disease with substantial physical and psychological burden. Genetic risk loci and a genome-wide association study have disclosed more than 60 genetic loci associated with psoriasis. Most of these loci are associated with immune system function. The genetic heterogeneity between patients gives rise to various pathogenic mechanisms. Numerous reports have mentioned the associations of psoriasis with other diseases, suggesting that psoriasis may synchronize the host immune system. A study performed later showed that administering biologic drugs to key immune system components will help alleviate psoriasis. In this review, we address quite recent emergence as novel advances of psoriasis: biologic drugs, genetics knowledge-derived for treatment, and novel approaches, and technologies in the field. These advancement has significantly contributed to elucidation of multifactorial nature of psoriasis and has provided the basis to develop newer and improved treatments. For instance, separate molecular genetics research emerging in the last decade determined definite gene and genetic polymorphisms incriminated in the pathogenesis and evolution of psoriasis. This knowledge could be useful in generating new intercessions in treatment that would directly involve these genetic predispositions to ensure efficient treatments, which are lacking at the moment. Also, the latest available RNA interference technique and CRISPR present new hope for the treatment psoriasis. RNA interference targets genes which contribute to disease development and CRISPR-CAS9 provides an opportunity to modify the genes which are responsible for disease development or progression. These newly developed form of treatment strategies are especially promising for the future of treating psoriasis. The principles

More Information

How to cite this article: Al-Subaihawi AJK, Almohammed TG, Al-Shabbani NHS. Advances in Psoriasis Treatment: Emerging Therapeutic Strategies Underlying Histopathological Changes in Psoriasis. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2024;2(6):58-69.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).07

Keywords:

chronic inflammatory skin disease, autoimmune disorder, genetic predispositions, bioprinting, innovative therapeutic strategies.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

of bioprinting or the generation of three-dimensional skin tissue by means of biocompatible materials and progenitor cells is another active area of psoriasis investigation. This technology has great potential to change the treatment of psoriasis because the skin tissue will always be at hand thus minimizing the use of donor grafts and the danger of rejection. In a similar way it is possible to produce organs with certain properties of interest for their functionality, for instance with an increased barrier function or an improved immune response of the transplant recipient, that would make treatment even more effective. In conclusion, the recent developments in understanding of pathophysiology of psoriasis have considerably brightened the choices of treatment and significantly enhance the quality of life of persons with this severe skin disease. Further research into the nature of the disease and the creation of new approaches for treating it can be considered as steps toward cure of psoriasis and improving the quality of life for the millions of people it affects. The histopathological improvements correspond with clinical improvement, as patients often experience reduced scaling, erythema, and thickness of lesions. While complete histological normalization may not always occur, a significant improvement is typically observed.

Introduction to Psoriasis

Psoriasis is a long-lasting autoimmune disorder that can be seriously debilitating despite the fact that it is not normally fatal. The disease is postulated to develop in genetically predisposed individuals who have autoimmune diathesis, linked with multiple genetic loci, partly known, and various environmental triggers. Psoriasis has an impact on 2.5-3% of the populace and seems to vary geographically. New findings on psoriasis indicate that the disease has high rates of comorbidity with other diseases like psoriatic arthritis and other immune-mediated inflammation diseases like Crohn's disease and multiple sclerosis, and also malignant tumors, and diabetes, among others. Furthermore, there are a lot of patients with great psychological burden in psoriasis and the prevalence of any psychological disorders is approximately double as often as among reference population [1-2]. Besides skin the pathology affects different organ systems with complications and manifestations. Evidence suggests that mental health associated with this disease may cause psoriasis to be more linked with cardiovascular diseases, kidney disease, sympathetic syndrome, and even pregnancy complications. Moreover, psoriasis has to be realized as a system diseases the capacity of which is to affect not only the skin but also other aspects of health [3]. Moreover, psoriasis has to be treated not only from the point of view of the skin's symptoms, but also from the perspective of the psychological state of the patients. Topical agents form the building block of mild to moderate psoriasis although latest systemic agents such as the biologics and small molecules have transformed the management of severe disease. These molecular therapies have been remarkably effective in attaining durable disease-free survival and enhancing the well-being of patients struggling with the onerous manifestations of this chronic ailment [2]. Still, while more options continue to emerge, access to consonant treatment and affordable medications remains a concern among most patients. Prevalence and outcome of the disorder vary depending on different

healthcare settings, and some categories of the population may not receive proper and timely care for the psoriasis. These disparities must be rectified in order to provide all persons afflicted with psoriasis the equal chance of achieving good control and improved overall quality of life [4]. Therefore it is evident that psoriasis is not limited to the physical manifestation but rather a complex disease that affects different aspects in the life of a patient. These implications mean that to care for patients with psoriasis one must be aware of the systemic involvement, comorbidity of this disease and the psychological aspects it entails. Further, in order to make changes for the better in the results among patients diagnosed with this chronic disease, and to break barriers related to the accessibility of treatment and healthcare disparities, certain considerations are necessary. Through the promotion of continued investigations, discovery of new interventions, and improvement of individual focus, we can remember a world where the weight of this disease is diminish, and the benefit to patients is optimize [5]. Firstly, the vast and, occasionally, diverse genetic, metabolic and other antecedents apart from the basic disease intricacy can alter the patient response and modulate the disease-experience. In particular, during the final several decades, human migration has been the leading force affecting the genetic base and environment; naturally, this factor may impact the clinical picture of psoriasis. The various onset of the diseases or the variance in its severity in different places, coupled with the observed higher prevalence and severity of psoriasis in certain of these regions, broaden the scope on psoriasis, hence, the research question, how can psoriasis be better managed, in a diverse global community. Thus, the treatment of psoriasis should be intercultural and individualized according to the socio-demographic characteristics of patients in the region, which can result from the improved clinical outcomes according to therapy and faster recovery of Patients' Social Functions [6-7]. All this explains why there is a host of factors that can either enhance/worsen or alter the expressiveness of a

particular disease in an individual patient. The global change has weakened the racial barrier the recent decades' mobility of people because this mobility has affected the genetic make up as well as the environment this may have an impact on the presentation of psoriasis. The emergence of psoriasis on the global level and, moreover, the worsening of the disease and the increase in the severity of the pathological process in a number of areas significantly expands not only the genes of the disease itself, but also the environment in which people live, in other words, the unfavorable conditions influence the clinics of psoriasis. On this basis, there is a need to discuss the algorithm for the treatment of psoriasis in multicultural space. The difference of the onset and gravity of the disease in different countries and the sharp increase in the number of registered patients in certain regions greatly enhances the sphere of psoriasis. Therefore, it is necessary to continue this study with understanding how to deliver the treatment of psoriasis is appropriate for the multiethnic population [8-9]. From these factors, it seems reasonable to learn how to treat psoriasis with an intercultural and individual approach. The mobility of people in the recent decades and because this mobility has affected the genetic make up as well as the environment this may have an effect on the presentation of psoriasis. The global onset as well as the severity of the disease and the dramatic growth in cases in certain regions greatly extend the sphere of psoriasis. On this basis, there is a need to examine strategies for the approach to the treatment of psoriasis in a multicultural context. In recent decades, it has significantly impacted both the genetic makeup and environmental conditions, thereby potentially altering the clinical presentation of psoriasis. The varying onset and severity of the disease across different countries, coupled with the notable increase in reported cases in specific regions, significantly expands the scope of psoriasis. Consequently, this encourages further exploration into how to approach psoriasis treatment within a multiethnic context [8,9]. Given these considerations, it becomes crucial for the treatment of psoriasis to adopt an intercultural and personalized strategy. This strategy should help us consider socio-demographic characteristics of potential local patients should lead to better response of patients to therapy and their further ability to continue their previous activities. In such practice, there must be adequate emphasis on worthwhile aspects of patient care that would require a satisfaction of the principle of patients from diverse backgrounds and circumstances to yield the better results of general patient welfare [10-11].

Definition and Epidemiology

Psoriasis is considered a chronic, lifelong systemic condition that carries an increased risk of many broader health issues, which can have a significant and long-lasting impact on the affected person's life. It is a relapsing, remitting cutaneous inflammatory condition with skin and joint involvement, causing red, scaly plaques, and pain and inflammation of the synovial joints and at the tendinous sites. It is estimated that about 3% of the world's population suffers from this immune-mediated inflammatory disease. Genetic and immune-inflammatory factors are responsible for the development of the illness, especially when environmental factors act as triggers, causing an exacerbation of the symptoms. Psoriasis remains a disease that entails diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. To date, psoriatic arthritis and scalp involvement are the most frequent comorbidities, as the core of the illness is defined by the presence of cytokines that affect the immune system, keratinocyte growth, and skin proliferation [12].

The seminal theory of "psoriatic march" suggested that the skin was the protagonist in an inflamed interplay that originated after a breach of the skin barrier, initiating a cascade of immunologic events in the skin and within the greater patient, ultimately culminating in joint inflammation. Over the past years, it has become clear that the emerging explanation is a tale of the immune system gone awry in the skin and other target organs, where the interplay of stromal, adaptive, and innate immunity cells acquired the role of protagonist. Currently, an international consensus recognizes the systemic theory, including musculoskeletal inflammation. Psoriasis is often the initial step leading to the manifestation of the illness, frequently in the last decades of pediatric age, followed by a journey of pain in adulthood [13].

Histopathology and Immunology

1. Epidermal Changes

- **Hyperkeratosis:** Thickening of the stratum corneum due to increased keratinocyte proliferation.
- **Parakeratosis:** Presence of nuclei in the stratum corneum, resulting from rapid cell turnover.
- **Acanthosis:** Thickening of the epidermis, especially in the Malpighian layer, due to keratinocyte hyperproliferation.
- **Elongated Rete Ridges:** Downward extensions of the epidermal rete ridges, giving a "saw-tooth" appearance.
- **Loss of Granular Layer:** The stratum granulosum layer may be absent or reduced.

2. Dermal Changes

Dilated Capillaries: The papillary dermis shows capillary dilatation, often accounting for the redness seen in lesions.

Munro's Microabscesses: Collections of neutrophils within the stratum corneum.

Spongiform Pustules of Kogoj: Neutrophilic microabscesses within the spinous layer.

Pathophysiology and Immunology

Disease pathogenesis and immunology have become pivotal concepts for the understanding and management of psoriasis. Considerable evidence has shown that psoriasis is T cell driven and that IL-12, IL-23, and type 1 and type 17 immune environments play fundamental roles in driving and maintaining the chronic plaque-expression phase of psoriasis. Many great advances in psoriasis pathophysiology and immunology have led to the emergence of immunopathogenic, biologically focused therapeutic approaches that target the modulation or inhibition of aberrant disease pathways believed to be central to disease expression. This strategy of biological manipulation of known pathogenic pathways has been shown to be highly effective and has led to the development of therapies that differentiate psoriasis as being the first condition treated by interleukin inhibitors capable of specifically and simultaneously acting on both aspects of psoriasis immunobiology: TH1 as well as TH17 [14-15].

Both the original biological strategy used in psoriasis, as well as the natural and continuously unfolding pharmacological potential of biological therapies, have opened the doors to other therapeutic options that will provide important lessons for the future. Although immunobiological therapies have greatly helped to fill the therapeutic void of psoriasis and to treat diseases hitherto untreatable in a successful and safe manner, these medications are not without limitations. Since no therapeutic intervention is curative, the continuance of remission or an effective cure that can significantly modify the disease will become desirable. As a structured and conventionally aggressive approach, involving the use of traditional systemic agents or established therapies to alleviate the disease, topical treatments dedicated to maintaining healing or a cure may play a role in the control and management of patients in an effective way [16-17].

Current Treatment Modalities

Even though the etiology of psoriasis remains obscure, numerous attempts have been made to establish safer and more effective therapeutic guidelines. Over the last decade, significant progress has been made in the molecular understanding of the disease, and a number of novel therapeutic targets have been identified. This led to the development of new treatment modalities for the management of psoriasis, including small molecules and advanced cell- and molecular-targeted biologic agents. Despite the great excitement and enthusiasm about these developments in the field of anti-psoriatic therapeutics, there is little or no guidance

available to the practicing clinician to help with the decision as to which intervention should be tried first or in combination with others. The purpose of this review is to provide readers with a comprehensive and broad overview of current therapeutic options for psoriasis, to support further investigation in the field, and ultimately to aim towards a more natural, efficient, and timely transition between forms of antipsoriatic management and finally a tailored, individualized treatment algorithm in the near future. In this critical review, we provide a detailed overview of both established and novel therapeutic approaches, including a comprehensive account of the currently marketed biologics for the treatment of psoriasis. It is our hope that this review will stimulate further research, providing more information to help increase the speed and likelihood of a successful transition from traditional to the next step in the combinations of antipsoriatic treatment. The ultimate goal would be to define a tailored individual therapy for psoriasis and finding the best possible combination of treatments to address not only the improvement of the clinical features of the disease but also its associated comorbidities such as cardiovascular disease or metabolic syndrome. On this, we must not neglect that it inevitably entails also the discussion of cost-effectiveness of each treatment approach [18-21].

Topical Treatments

Topical treatments are an appropriate approach for patients with mild to moderate disease. Therapeutic trifarotene lotion, a fourth-generation retinoid, has recently been added to the psoriasis armamentarium. This chapter will address the current limitations of the available topical treatments in the face of ongoing theoretical and clinical progress in the transplantation of microbiota, imiquimod's possible anti-inflammatory effect through the correction of tryptophan metabolism, the strategies to solve the irritancy generated by benzoyl alcohol, and topical vitamin D and systemic antipsoriatic combinations. The combination of a topical corticosteroid and vitamin D analogue calcipotriol is the approach that is most often recommended for treating psoriasis plaques. In this chapter, an update is proposed about new therapeutic options in the face of previous limitations of topical treatments. In this context, clinical trials in the transplantation of bacteria, results with imiquimod regarding tryptophan metabolism, and observations regarding irritancy by benzyl alcohol are discussed. Additionally, the possible combination RNA/DNA mechanisms are proposed to explain molecular synergistic problems of this tissue recognition receptor topically oriented for its anti-inflammatory action in the antipsoriatic axis. In vitro data and hypotheses regarding the synergistic activation of the RXRs by the

combination of vitamin D and RORC in epidermal keratinocytes are discussed [22-24].

Phototherapy

Phototherapy is another well-established therapy in use for patients with moderate or severe psoriasis. It is often recommended to individuals who have failed conventional topical therapy, individuals with extensive plaque psoriasis, and those with psoriasis that is recalcitrant to topical therapy. In phototherapy, the skin is systematically irradiated with ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Typically, narrowband ultraviolet B (NBUVB) is the UV light source of choice for treating psoriatic plaques, although broad-band ultraviolet B, although still effective, is not as effective. Increasing evidence suggests combination therapy with tazarotene cream and NBUVB phototherapy provides faster and more robust clinical clearing of psoriatic skin than either single treatment entity alone, although head-to-head clinical studies are warranted. Also, the use of prior or simultaneous UVB therapy with ustekinumab may result in faster clinical results [25-27].

Although whole body UV irradiation is potentially hazardous, stable plaque psoriasis is one disease where the benefits of NBUVB therapy outweigh the risks. As NBUVB irradiation becomes increasingly effective, it is important that dermatologists continue to be aware of the unique shortcomings of this therapeutic modality so that patients are treated in the most effective manner. The spread of ultraviolet B radiation causes activation of immunosuppressive agents, a key anti-inflammatory effect, and is further believed to induce keratinocytes to undergo apoptosis-necroptosis, thus accelerating the resolution of lesions while minimizing progression to malignancies such as cutaneous T-cell lymphoma. In controlled clinical trials, NBUVB therapy has proven to be beneficial for treating psoriasis and is commonly prescribed either as monotherapy or in combination with other topical or oral treatments. Its increased efficacy and good tolerability have resulted in the wide adoption of NBUVB therapy for treating mild-to-severe psoriatic lesions today [28-29].

Systemic Medications

Proper use of systemic therapies is an important component for successful management of moderate to severe plaque psoriasis for patients who cannot be managed sufficiently with phototherapies or topical agents alone. The systemic agents available for psoriasis to date provide varying degrees of efficacy, some unfortunately at the expense of major side effects. The first and foremost new class of systemic medications in the management of psoriasis that we will discuss is the biologicals, which have already been introduced to provide specific action on different aspects of the pathophysiology of psoriasis. There are two main general methods that suppress these stages: targeting T-cell function via immunosuppressive

effects, thus leading to immunosuppression, and the manipulation of downstream T-cell produced cytokines. The therapy used for psoriasis, historically starting from hundreds of years ago, has contributed the most to our current understanding of treating psoriasis with systemic medications [30-31].

Patients show an amelioration of their skin disease in response to drugs that are well-known to suppress allogeneic T cells, such as systemic corticosteroids, cyclosporine, methotrexate, or other immunosuppressive therapies. Among the patients with a mixed inflammatory cell infiltrate, T cells should be the most predominant cell type in the dermis, and an effector cell population appears to be extremely important in the pathogenesis of psoriasis. In accordance, immunosuppressive systemic medications help to ameliorate psoriasis. These drugs frequently suppress the whole immune system and are associated with numerous side effects as a result, such as opportunities for infections, nephrotoxicity, hair loss, infertility, and malignant neoplasia. The biologicals, in effect, are the first agents capable of specifically targeting the psoriasis disease process without altering or suppressing other parts of the immune system [32-33].

Emerging Therapeutic Strategies

The exceptional progress in visualizing the complex underlying pathogenesis in recent years has fueled the emergence of innovative and highly effective therapeutic options for inducing remission or at least a predictable response in psoriasis. These new physically targeted therapies and signals identified throughout the resolution of skin inflammation could be promising sources for novel leading strategies in developing new drugs for psoriasis. With the identification of novel and key signals orchestrating skin barrier repair, a promising new era of integrating biological technology into adult or atopic skin is significantly at its outset. Personalized skincare strategies, notably clinical outcomes, will depend on our ability to understand and identify these signals. The next generation of combination therapy inhibiting multiple diseases will specifically highlight induction strategies for the biology of interleukins and also advance our knowledge in the field by developing new in vitro skin model systems that can be continuously stimulated to design better-targeted therapies directly or to their complex, as well as to facilitate a sustainable clinical view of the underlying mechanisms. Recent advances in microbiome therapy, focusing on viral and state-of-the-art immune profiling, will enable a validated treatment of the disease in the genetics of human beings [34-35].

Biologic Therapies

Biological treatments for psoriasis, such as TNF inhibitors, IL-17, IL-12/23, and IL-23 inhibitors, have significantly improved outcomes for patients. These

treatments target specific parts of the immune system involved in psoriasis pathogenesis, leading to notable histopathological changes in psoriatic skin. Here's an overview of the main changes observed:

1. Reduction in Epidermal Hyperplasia

Psoriasis is characterized by thickening of the epidermis (acanthosis) and elongation of rete ridges. After biological treatment, there is a marked reduction in epidermal thickness and normalization of the rete ridges, leading to a more typical epidermal structure.

2. Decreased Inflammatory Infiltrate

Psoriatic lesions have a dense inflammatory infiltrate, primarily consisting of T-cells, dendritic cells, neutrophils, and other immune cells. Biological treatments reduce this inflammatory cell infiltration, especially in the dermis, resulting in an overall decrease in inflammation.

3. Reduction in Vascular Changes

Psoriasis often leads to increased dermal blood vessel dilation and angiogenesis. After biological treatment, there is a normalization of blood vessel density and size, contributing to reduced redness and scaling in lesions.

4. Decrease in Keratinocyte Proliferation

Keratinocyte hyperproliferation is a hallmark of psoriasis. Treatment with biologics often leads to a reduction in keratinocyte turnover and proliferation, observed as normalization in the thickness of the stratum corneum.

5. Reduction in Expression of Psoriasis-Associated Markers

Psoriasis lesions have high levels of certain markers, like Ki-67 (a proliferation marker), and pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., TNF-alpha, IL-17, and IL-23). After biological therapy, these markers decrease significantly, which is a direct indicator of reduced inflammatory activity and disease severity.

6. Restoration of Barrier Function

Some biological treatments, particularly those targeting IL-17, are noted to improve skin barrier function by normalizing lipid metabolism and the differentiation of keratinocytes, thereby reducing transepidermal water loss (TEWL).

The increasing understanding of the pathogenesis of psoriasis has led to the development of new, more targeted biologic treatments. Thermal springs and phototherapy have been used for a long time to treat psoriasis, demonstrating the potential benefit of light in this skin disease. The introduction of biologics has led to major advances in the treatment of severe forms of psoriasis, with the possibility of long-term control of the disease. Two non-B cell-targeting biotechnologies, namely tumor necrosis factor inhibitors and a fusion protein targeting different pro-inflammatory cytokines, are currently available on the market for systemic treatment of moderate to severe psoriasis: the

monoclonal antibody ustekinumab, which targets the common chain of the cytokine receptors of IL-12 and IL-23, and secukinumab and ixekizumab, which block the activity of interleukin 17A, respectively. Ustekinumab was recently introduced into the therapeutic arsenal to inhibit the pathogenic functions of Th-1 and Th-17 lymphocytes by targeting the p40 subunit shared by the two interleukins. Among the biotechnologies also applied in psoriasis, rituximab and a CD6 targeting monoclonal antibody will also be addressed. Their respective availability as well as medicinal interactions are critical in choosing the biopersistence in psoriasis [36-38].

Biologics, particularly anti-TNF- α drugs, have revolutionized systemic therapy for psoriasis. All approved biologics have substantial evidence to show they are safe and effective in the treatment of psoriasis. The effectiveness of biologics, mainly anti-TNF- α in reducing inflammatory processes, has inspired the evaluation of biosimilar compounds, for which the potential to increase patient access and reduce therapy costs, without losing clinical benefit, remains the main goal. In clinical practice, all psoriasis drug therapies appear to be effective in achieving fast and durable disease control. High drug efficacy is particularly beneficial in reducing the likelihood of relapse due to the difficulty in using a treatment cut-off. Biologics-based long-term management of chronic skin inflammation in psoriasis faces the usual clinical challenges, such as the development of drug-induced adverse effects and the management of complex pharmacological interactions in frail patients, particularly when psoriasis predisposes to cardiovascular comorbid disease. Both the effects and the risks of combining biologic therapy and radiotherapy are not documented. The anti-psoriatic efficacy of radiotherapy has been well demonstrated in terms of stable response, despite the low rate of acute radiation toxicity skin and systematic treatment. [38-41].

Small Molecule Inhibitors

Small molecule inhibitors are an older treatment option for psoriasis, with the most famous member being cyclosporine, which is also known as a calcineurin inhibitor. For psoriasis, cyclosporine is an effective and fast-acting treatment. However, due to its nephrotoxic effects, cyclosporine has not been a long-term solution. Lack of treatment response, side effects, and the time required for a treatment holiday have been the disadvantages of cyclosporine. At the molecular level, cyclosporine binds to cyclophilin and results in suppression of the nuclear factor of activated T cells. By inhibiting T-lymphocyte function, the inflammatory response is suppressed [42-43].

Tofacitinib is an oral JAK 1 and 3 kinase inhibitor. In phase 3 trials of tofacitinib, psoriasis was treated at

doses of 5 mg, 10 mg, and 15 mg. Tofacitinib has been shown to produce a greater PASI75 ratio versus placebo with the goal of 10 mg twice a day. During the long-term use of up to 104 weeks, its efficacy, tolerability, and safety were still adequate. The most common side effects were upper respiratory infections, headache, and nasopharyngitis. Genital infections, herpes zoster, and urinary problems have developed, but the frequency of developing serious infections was low. In particular, the 10 mg dose was preferred to reach the higher response rates, but the patients were also included in the study with the 5 mg dose due to low dose tolerability. Apart from these effects, tofacitinib also affects biological and immunological processes of psoriasis more completely. Major patients have been treated with a single agent, tofacitinib, or in conjunction with other systemic psoriasis treatments. Admissions due to lack of effectiveness and adverse events were omitted and reduced. Tofacitinib is a drug that has been shown to eliminate psoriasis completely or almost completely for the first time in a long-term study. In psoriasis therapy, decreases were detected in mean IL-23, IL-17, IL-22, IL-1, TNF α , and IL-6. The safety profile of tofacitinib was protective for over 2.5 years or more. Furthermore, the frequency of adverse events that developed decreased over time. Tofacitinib, which reduced the adverse effects by using supportive treatment strategies, improved treatment adherence while receiving HRQOL improvements. Long-term suppression of chronic inflammation is associated with a reduction in established comorbidities in dermatologic psoriasis. The rapid reduction and normalization of immune cell subsets and soluble mediators of inflammation can be achieved with JAK 1/3 inhibitors. Large-scale studies can confirm full austerity and evidence-based guidelines. Due to the uncertain conditions and the possibility of new adverse events not seen in clinical trials, the use of multiple drugs over time can be considered if necessary [44-46].

Gene Therapy

Genetherapy has come a long way, especially in its transition from human genome identification to clinical applications. In recent decades, there have been remarkable advancements and breakthroughs in the field of genetherapy, revolutionizing the way we approach the treatment of various genetic disorders. Psoriasis, a chronic inflammatory skin condition, provides a near-perfect platform for gene therapy, given its well-known role in various key signaling cascades [47]. One of the major advantages of gene therapy in psoriasis is that it offers the potential for long-term and even permanent relief from the symptoms of the disease. Traditional psoriasis therapies often provide unsatisfactory clinical responses and may entail risks associated with their long-term use. On the other hand, gene therapy may

appear rather as a viable and promising enough approach to this crippling illness in affected patients with psoriasis [48]. Despite the stated realities the role of gene therapy in psoriasis treatment may look like the following. The first strategy for correcting the pathology involves the transfer of psoriasis correcting genes which can directly tackle a molecular abnormality causing disease. Second, there is an opportunity to delete harm-causing effects of certain genes, which cause psoriatic changes, and to restore normal functional activity and balanced regulation of signaling pathways that lead to psoriatic manifestations' disappearance [49]. The second type of gene therapy in psoriasis seems to imply inhibition of genes that initiate the inflammation process. This can be done by directing the techniques of gene editing for instance crispr cas 9, meaning altering gene materials. However by selectively and selectively suppressing these pathogenic genes the condition of increased inflammation present in the psoriasis patients can be managed and thus provide some comfort to the patients [50]. This means that in gene therapy for the management of psoriasis better and efficient methods of gene delivery need to be developed. It may also be a break through because other than applications of non-viral vectors could be more beneficial than viral vectors that has only integrity for gene delivery. The non-viral vectors like liposomes and nanoparticles also seem to help in improving the security and efficacy of gene therapy by minimizing immunogenicity and NEW events' possibilities [51]. However, the difficulty in using these vector techniques still remain cumbersome in terms of efficiency, and the complexity in directly transferring in vivo transduction techniques. Authorities are attempting to create new techniques in order to overcome these barriers and these methods are the use of the physical procedures such as electroporation as well as the utilization of cell penetrating peptides that can enhance the delivery of the therapeutic genes to the target cells [52]. However, special attention and strict critique should be necessarily paid to the use of viral vectors in the treatment of psoriasis with the help of gene therapy. Because gene therapy operates by altering the exact genetic makeup of skin cells, its negative impacts need to be downplayed vis-a-vis the intended-on-target and unintended-off-target effects. One has to ensure regular and strict evaluation of the safety profile of viral vectors in order to ensure the welfare of patients who undergo gene therapy [48]. The possibilities for corrections and improvements on the vectors that are used to administer gene therapy is continually improving and this cannot be denied that offers great potential in improving the management of psoriasis. This being the case, the possibility of pin pointing and changing the genetic makers that cause the disease

extends a glimmer of hope and a chance at a healing for the millions of people living with psoriasis. Gradually as research unfolds and more information accumulates about the disease, gene therapy may turn out to be a revolutionized treatment that offers long term cure to patients suffering from psoriasis at the global level with a better quality of life [53-55].

Combination Therapies

Given the widespread and highly prevalent nature of psoriasis in its various phenotypical expressions and the multitude of intricate pathogenetic pathways involved, the therapeutic management of this chronic inflammatory skin disease represents a highly intricate and multifaceted medical endeavor. In addition to the remarkably high incidence of comorbidities that typically accompany psoriasis, the exposome (the totality of environmental exposures from conception to death) and its profound impact on therapeutic strategies exacerbate the already complex landscape. In recent years, an abundance of studies has been conducted to explore innovative treatment strategies, encompassing a multitude of comprehensive clinical trials aimed at targeting specific pathophysiological mechanisms [56]. Ascertaining the results from long-term monitoring of extensive bibliographic registers and robust real-world data represents an invaluable resource, especially in the post-marketing stage of drug development. These sources provide evidence-based statements of unparalleled efficacy and safety standards, allowing healthcare professionals to make informed decisions when selecting appropriate treatment options for patients with psoriasis. In addition, the traditional medical model has been replaced by precision medicine and other individualised approaches that have introduced an era of treatments that respond to a patients genes, life style and even those triggered by the environment around the patient [11]. Also, clinicians and researchers have teamed up with patients thus ensuring that patients are involved in advancing the course of psoriasis. Teamwork in interprofessional teams facilitates the approach to necessary cooperation where people of different backgrounds with different knowledge and abilities could improve the clients' performance. Thus, developing the models of shared decision making concerning treatment plans is helpful in supporting the patient with psoriasis to be involved in the implementation of their own treatment strategies [57]. However, as far as the patients are concerned, improving their level of knowledge is the issue of great concern as well. Developing patient awareness regarding the more likely long-term, often asymptomatic, nature of psoriasis and potential triggers with contemporaneous treatments enhances patient self-management. This inturn can increase time for interventional treatments and adherence to

medication regimens which in effect could enhance the quality of life for persons living with psoriasis [38]. Therefore, the management of psoriasis is a dynamic therapeutic process that requires a comprehensive approach that considers the various phenotypes the multiple molecular processes underlying the condition comorbidities exposome factors and existing advanced therapeutic approaches in dermatology. Cohesive collaboration, proactive individualized medical approach, patient enlightenment and recognition of the POL trigger causes help the healthcare team to be more effective in the management of patients with psoriasis [58].

Nevertheless, a guideline approach based on clinical studies of combination strategies in therapeutic decisions has not been adequately addressed, as well as insufficient documentation of the real-life scenario derived from long-term monitoring with therapeutic complexity that is impossible to reproduce in studies conducted by the usual pre-establishment models in drug licensing. Only after years of a combination of different strategies can we assess the likelihood of target organ damage for the patient from chronic inflammatory disease. Taking into account that the current concept of collaboration expects profitability in the long term for all parties involved, the term 'combinatorial therapy' is substituted by 'combined therapy.' It should be taken into account that current disease concepts are considering a multifactorial approach in therapeutic decision-making [59-61].

Patient Education and Adherence

In addition to screening and treatment recommendations, primary care physicians can play a meaningful and critical role in patients' healthcare journeys by providing effective and comprehensive education about the multitude of treatment benefits. Patient education is of utmost importance as it encompasses a wide array of essential aspects such as disease severity, therapeutic goals, treatment benefits, as well as the potential outcomes of untreated diseases. Ensuring that patients are well-informed about their conditions and the merits of various treatment options will not only foster adherence but also mitigate the risk of potential misunderstandings regarding serious side effects associated with long-term prescription treatments [2]. The general education process is also an untapped opportunity because it can manage decisional ambivalence because in patients with a low to moderate severity of the disease. While patient decision counseling has been used and demonstrated to lead to increased concordance with single psoriasis preference choices, this work has also shown that patient decision counseling, if designed and approached through a sustainable model grounded within a brief and structured psychosocial model, aligns with the goals of

patient decision support foundations. Therefore, this approach could be regarded as a great challenge and a unique chance to focus on patient choice in treatment plans. [62] Inviting the patient, whose life is affected by the certain disease, to the discussion of treatment possibilities, using his opinion as valuable tools to make a final decision, physicians can promote the patient-oriented approach, increase the effectiveness of the chosen treatment and probability of patient's satisfaction. Thus, this vision of collaboration will mean that patients will be able to learn more about their status and available treatment options so that they could make the right choices that reflect the patient's preference and their personal values [63]. In addition, the primary care physicians can use more innovative ways and means of conveying patient education. Psoriasis preference choices. Consequently, this approach represents a remarkable opportunity for healthcare professionals to prioritize and align with patients' preferences when prescribing treatments [62]. By actively engaging patients in conversations about their treatment options and considering their perspectives as vital tools to arrive at the most informed decision, physicians can empower patients to be active participants in their healthcare journey, ultimately resulting in improved treatment outcomes and overall satisfaction. This collaborative approach will allow patients to have a deeper understanding of their conditions and the available treatments, enabling them to make informed choices that align with their personal preferences and values [63]. Furthermore, primary care physicians can utilize innovative educational resources and technologies to enhance the delivery of patient education. New technologies such as social media, applications and virtual reality thereby can help in creating awareness and safeguard patient compliance since they are easily understandable. In particular, by employing these resources, the physicians can develop and provide educational information that can reach the patient in his or her preferred method of learning and understanding thus improving his or her learning as well as knowledge capacity of concerns issues and others. Pertinently, the primary care physicians can make arrangements of support groups and educational seminars for such patients with objectives of sharing experiences and acquiring knowledge from other patients and healthcare givers respectively. Such group settings promote community Attendance and Self Empowerment hence giving patients a chance to meet other patients struggling with similar health complications, get to understand different ways of dealing with such complications. The council and assistance received from these exchanges can profit the patients' rehabilitation in a major way. Therefore, the primary care physicians are important for giving proper

and effective education to the patients. When educating both the patient and the family, involving the patient in decision making and using techniques such as motivational interviewing, social media and other tools patients can be engaged in their care. This approach will lead to improved treatment outcomes, enhanced patient satisfaction, and ultimately, a higher quality of care [65-67].

Conclusion

The development of new targeted therapies and several innovative therapeutic strategies contribute to considerable advances in psoriasis treatment and further improve the health, quality of life, and well-being of many patients in need. It may also stimulate further research to better understand the disease and eventually lead to the discovery of more sophisticated treatments. Even more recently, several new investigational studies identified genes and signaling pathways triggered in keratinocytes, adding new possible targets for future treatment of psoriasis and other skin diseases. In summary, these studies identified potential new pathways, either previously unknown or less known, opening new perspectives for studies of skin diseases, both for basic research and in the search for new treatments that could be more effective and safe. This repositioning therapeutic approach allowed for the rescue of five approved drugs for use in an inflammatory context of the skin and the highlighting of other targets that may also be pharmacologically accessible. These findings highlight the medical potential of drug repositioning, encourage its exploration, and should drive future breakthroughs for treating various skin diseases in addition to psoriasis. This work may, therefore, represent a pioneering reservoir not only of rescued drugs but also of potential next-generation treatments, providing a significant contribution to the interconnection of different scientific communities to deliver not only innovative pharmaceutical solutions but also an improvement in the efficacy of skin disease treatment strategies.

References

- [1] Armstrong AW, Mehta MD, Schupp CW. Psoriasis prevalence in adults in the United States. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2021;157(7):873-875. doi: 10.1001/jamadermatol.2021.1702
- [2] Reid C, Griffiths CEM. Psoriasis and treatment: past, present and future aspects. *Acta Derm Venereol.* 2020;100(5). doi: 10.2340/00015555-3456
- [3] Zwain A, Aldiwani M, Taqi H. The association between psoriasis and cardiovascular diseases. *Eur Cardiol Rev.* 2021;16. doi: 10.15420/ocr.2021.16
- [4] Essien UR, Dusetzina SB, Gellad WF. A policy prescription for reducing health disparities—achieving

pharmacoequity. *JAMA*. 2021;326(19):1867-1868. doi: 10.1001/jama.2021.16757

[5] Taliercio VL, Snyder AM, Webber LB. The disruptiveness of itchiness from psoriasis: a qualitative study of the impact of a single symptom on quality of life. *J Investig Dermatol Symp Proc*. 2021;22(1).

[6] Caputo V, Strafella C, Termine A. Overview of the molecular determinants contributing to the expression of Psoriasis and Psoriatic Arthritis phenotypes. *J Cell Mol Med*. 2020;24(22):13054-13063. doi: 10.1111/jcmm.15734

[7] Roszkiewicz M, Dopytalska K. Environmental risk factors and epigenetic alterations in psoriasis. *Ann Agric Environ Med*. 2020;27(1):123-129.

[8] Dopytalska K, Ciechanowicz P, Wiszniewski K. The role of epigenetic factors in psoriasis. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(2):929. doi: 10.3390/ijms22020929

[9] Antonatos C, Grafanaki K, Asmenoudi P. Contribution of the Environment, Epigenetic Mechanisms and Non-Coding RNAs in Psoriasis. *Biomedicines*. 2022;10(4):965. doi: 10.3390/biomedicines10040965

[10] Gisondi P, Fargnoli MC, Amerio P. Italian adaptation of EuroGuiDerm guideline on the systemic treatment of chronic plaque psoriasis. *Ital J Dermatol Venerol*. 2022;157(3):233-253.

[11] Reid C, Cordingley L, Warren RB. Progress to date in advancing stratified medicine in psoriasis. *Am J Clin Dermatol*. 2020;21(6):843-855. doi: 10.1007/s40257-020-00558-y

[12] Singh N, Sondhi S, Jindal S, Pandit V. Treatment and Management for patients with mild to severe Psoriasis: A Review. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2020;13(7):13-17.

[13] Klyne DM, Barbe MF, James G, Hodges PW. Does the interaction between local and systemic inflammation provide a link from psychology and lifestyle to tissue health in musculoskeletal conditions? *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(5):2525. doi: 10.3390/ijms22052525

[14] Hu P, Wang M, Gao H, Zheng A, Li J, Mu D. The role of helper T cells in psoriasis. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:788061. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2021.788061

[15] Bugaut H, Aractingi S. Major role of the IL17/23 axis in psoriasis supports the development of new targeted therapies. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:621956. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2021.621956

[16] Esmaeilzadeh A, Bahmaie N, Nouri E. Immunobiological properties and clinical applications of interleukin-38 for immune-mediated disorders: a systematic review study. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(8):4272. doi: 10.3390/ijms22084272

[17] Anupam K, Kaushal J, Tandon A. Current Challenges in Immunobiology of Autoimmunity and Cancer. *Med Dis*. 2023;11(1).

[18] Rossi S, Antal A, Bestmann S, Bikson M, Brewer C, et al. Expert Guidelines for TMS use in healthy subjects and patient populations, with updates on training, ethical and regulatory issues: Expert Guidelines. *Clin Neurophysiol*. 2021;132(1):243-271. doi: 10.1016/j.clinph.2020.10.003

[19] Gorski LA, Hadaway L, Hagle ME. Infusion therapy standards of practice. *J Infus Nurs*. 2021;44(1S Suppl 1).

[20] Cook TM, El-Boghdadly K, McGuire B. Consensus guidelines for managing the airway in patients with COVID-19: Guidelines from the Difficult Airway Society, the Association of Anaesthetists the Intensive. *Anaesthesia*. 2020;75(6):785-799. doi: 10.1111/anae.15054

[21] World Health Organization. Patient safety incident reporting and learning systems: technical report and guidance. Geneva: WHO; 2020. [DOI отсутствует] [who.int]

[22] See JA, Chavda R, Kon KM. A review of the topical management of acne and its associated sequelae in the Asia-Pacific region with a spotlight on trifarotene. *Int J Dermatol*. 2024;63(1):105-112.

[23] Bhatt S, Kothari R, Tripathy DM, Sandhu S. Emerging drugs for the treatment of acne: a review of phase 2 & 3 trials. *Expert Opin Investig Drugs*. 2022;31(3):245-258. doi: 10.1080/13543784.2022.2024706

[24] Petrou I. Advances in Rosacea Therapy. *Dermatol Times*. 2023;44(1).

[25] Krenitsky A, Ghamrawi RI, Feldman SR. Phototherapy: a review and update of treatment options in dermatology. *Curr Dermatol Rep*. 2020;9(2):51-57. doi: 10.1007/s13671-020-00289-5

[26] Sreya R, Nene S, Pathade V, Singh SB. Emerging trends in combination strategies with phototherapy in advanced psoriasis management. *Photodermatol Photoimmunol Photomed*. 2023;39(4):282-289.

[27] Ahad T, Kalia S, Lui H. Topical, Ablative and Light-Based Therapies for Non-Melanoma Skin Neoplasms. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2023;15(2):456. doi: 10.3390/cancers15020456

[28] Yanovsky RL, Huang KP, Buzney EA. Optimizing narrowband UVB phototherapy regimens for psoriasis. *Dermatol Clin*. 2020;38(1):21-29.

[29] Li Y, Cao Z, Guo J, Li Q, Zhu W, Kuang Y. Assessment of efficacy and safety of UV-based therapy for psoriasis: a network meta-analysis of randomized

- controlled trials. *Ann Med.* 2022;54(1):1382-1393. doi: 10.1080/07853890.2022.2110605
- [30] Korman NJ. Management of psoriasis as a systemic disease: what is the evidence? *Br J Dermatol.* 2020;182(4):845-853. doi: 10.1111/bjd.18311
- [31] van Winden MEC, van der Schoot LS. Effectiveness and safety of systemic therapy for psoriasis in older adults: a systematic review. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2020;156(5):543-554. doi: 10.1001/jamadermatol.2020.0000.
- [32] Kearns DG, Uppal S, Chat VS, Wu JJ. Use of systemic therapies for psoriasis in the COVID-19 era. *J Dermatolog Treat.* 2022 Mar;33(2):702-709. doi: 10.1080/09546634.2020.1857622
- [33] Skyvalidas DN, Mavropoulos A, Tsiogkas S. The attenuation of pro-inflammatory interferon γ and interleukin 17 cytokine responses in psoriatic disease, strengthening its role as a dietary immunosuppressant. *Nutr Res.* 2020 Sep;80:49-58. doi: 10.1016/j.nutres.2020.06.010
- [34] Chen L, Li J, Zhu W, Kuang Y, Liu T, Zhang W. Skin and gut microbiome in psoriasis: gaining insight into the pathophysiology and finding novel therapeutic strategies. *Front Immunol.* 2020;11:571427. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2020.571427
- [35] Sikora M, Stec A, Chrabaszc M, Knot A. Gut microbiome in psoriasis: an updated review. *Pathogens.* 2020;9(6):463. doi: 10.3390/pathogens9060463.
- [36] Bellinato F, Gisondi P, Girolomoni G. Latest advances for the treatment of chronic plaque psoriasis with biologics and oral small molecules. *Biologics: Targets Ther.* 2021;15:45-56. doi: 10.2147/BTT.S276870.
- [37] Hari G, Kishore A, Karkala SRP. Treatments for psoriasis: A journey from classical to advanced therapies. How far have we reached? *Eur J Pharmacol.* 2022;915:174582. doi: 10.1016/j.ejphar.2021.174582.
- [38] Lee HJ, Kim M. Challenges and future trends in the treatment of psoriasis. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023;24(6):3390. doi: 10.3390/ijms24063390.
- [39] Brownstone ND, Hong J, Mosca M. Biologic treatments of psoriasis: an update for the clinician. *Biologics: Targets Ther.* 2021;15:73-90. doi: 10.2147/BTT.S288615.
- [40] Diotallevi F, Paolinelli M, Radi G. Latest combination therapies in psoriasis: Narrative review of the literature. *Clin Ther.* 2022;44(2):207-221. doi: 10.1016/j.clinthera.2021.12.011.
- [41] Gisondi P, Geat D, Conti A, Dapavo P. TNF- α inhibitors biosimilars as first-line systemic treatment for moderate-to-severe chronic plaque psoriasis. *Expert Rev Clin Immunol.* 2020;16(8):839-847. doi: 10.1080/1744666X.2020.1792770.
- [42] Nakamura M, Koo J. Safety considerations with combination therapies for psoriasis. *Expert Opin Drug Saf.* 2020;19(5):603-612. doi: 10.1080/14740338.2020.1746523.
- [43] Namazi MR. Severe Psoriasis: Pearls. In: *Textbook of Advanced Dermatology: Pearls for Practice.* 2024.
- [44] Sarabia S, Ranjith B, Koppikar S, Wijeratne DT. Efficacy and safety of JAK inhibitors in the treatment of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Rheumatol.* 2022;6:18. doi: 10.1186/s41927-022-00226-2.
- [45] van der Togt CJT, Verhoef LM, et al. Pharmacokinetic boosting to enable a once-daily reduced dose of tofacitinib in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and psoriatic arthritis (the PRACTICAL study). *Ther Adv Musculoskelet Dis.* 2022;14:1-10. doi: 10.1177/1759720X221094576.
- [46] Todberg T, Loft ND, Zachariae C. Improvement of psoriasis, psoriatic arthritis, and alopecia universalis during treatment with tofacitinib: a case report. *Case Rep Dermatol.* 2020;12(1):1-5. doi: 10.1159/000507711.
- [47] Chew E, Perin J, Grader-Beck T. Measurement of minimal disease activity in psoriatic arthritis using PROMIS-Physical Function or the Health Assessment Questionnaire-Disability Index. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken).* 2022;74(9):1465-1473. doi: 10.1002/acr.24598.
- [48] Lin ZC, Hung CF, Aljuffali IA, Lin MH. RNA-Based Antipsoriatic Gene Therapy: An Updated Review Focusing on Evidence from Animal Models. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2024.
- [49] Tseng JC, Chang YC, Huang CM, Hsu LC, et al. Therapeutic development based on the immunopathogenic mechanisms of psoriasis. *Pharmaceutics.* 2021;13(8):1249. doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics13081249.
- [50] Tokuyama M, Mabuchi T. New treatment addressing the pathogenesis of psoriasis. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020;21(19):7035. doi: 10.3390/ijms21197035.
- [51] Tortajada L, Felip-León C, Vicent MJ. Polymer-based non-viral vectors for gene therapy in the skin. *Polym Chem.* 2022;13:1339-1351.
- [52] Heinrich M, Appendino G, Efferth T, Fürst R. Best practice in research—overcoming common challenges in phytopharmacological research. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2020;246:112230. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2020.112230.
- [53] Sawarkar SP, Yadav V. Novel drug delivery strategies and gene therapy regimen as a promising perspective for management of psoriasis. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol.* 2021;87(3):302-311. doi: 10.25259/IJDVL_854_20.
- [54] Naik PP. Stem cell therapy as a potential treatment option for psoriasis. *An Bras Dermatol.* 2022;97(1):45-51. doi: 10.1016/j.abd.2021.08.005.

- [55] Lwin SM, Snowden JA. The promise and challenges of cell therapy for psoriasis. *Br J Dermatol*. 2021;184(5):835-846. doi: 10.1111/bjd.19798.
- [56] Yadav K, Singh D, Singh MR. Novel archetype in psoriasis management bridging molecular dynamics in exploring novel therapies. *Eur J Pharmacol*. 2021;899:174048.
- [57] Prignano F, Campione E, Parodi A, Vegni E. EMPATHY Life in Psoriasis: Embracing Patients' Well-Being in Their Journey of Moderate-to-Severe Psoriasis. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(3):569.
- [58] Debela DT, Muzazu SGY, Heraro KD. New approaches and procedures for cancer treatment: Current perspectives. *SAGE Open*. 2021;11(3):215824402111045288.
- [59] Butterfield LH, Najjar YG. Immunotherapy combination approaches: mechanisms, biomarkers and clinical observations. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2024.
- [60] Kreiner DS, Matz P, Bono CM, Cho CH, Easa JE. Guideline summary review: an evidence-based clinical guideline for the diagnosis and treatment of low back pain. *Spine J*. 2020;20(6):893-899.
- [61] Grasselli G, Calfee CS, Camporota L, Poole D. ESICM guidelines on acute respiratory distress syndrome: definition, phenotyping and respiratory support strategies. *Intensive Care Med*. 2023;49(5):637-648.
- [62] Morrison T, Johnson J, Baghoomian W. Shared decision-making in dermatology: a scoping review. *JAMA Dermatol*. 2021;157(2):154-160.
- [63] Bewley A, van de Kerkhof P. Engaging psoriasis patients in adherence and outcomes to topical treatments: A summary from the Symposium 'Tailoring topical psoriasis treatments to patients'. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2023;37(Suppl 1):3-8.
- [64] Powers MA, Bardsley JK, Cypress M, et al. Consensus report of the Association of Diabetes Care & Education Specialists, the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics, the American Academy of Family Physicians, the American Academy of Pediatrics, and the American Diabetes Association. *Diabetes Spectr*. 2020;33(2):151-165.
- [65] Hawes EM, Sanders KA. Medication management and treatment adherence. In: *Chronic Illness Care: Principles and Practice*. 2023.
- [66] Hamrahian SM, Maarouf OH, Fülöp T. A critical review of medication adherence in hypertension: barriers and facilitators clinicians should consider. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 2022;16:2531-2544.
- [67] Baryakova TH, Pogostin BH, Langer R. Overcoming barriers to patient adherence: the case for developing innovative drug delivery systems. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. 2023;22(5):379-392.